

Editorial Acknowledgment

This issue features a regular article, two articles that will be presented at the [16th International Conference on Educational Data Mining \(EDM 2023\)](#) in the JEDM@EDM track that will take place in Bengaluru, India, July 11-14 2023, and two articles that are extended versions of papers that were presented at the [15th International Conference on Educational Data Mining \(EDM\)](#) that took place in a hybrid format in Durham, UK, July 24-27 2022, and that could not be published in the corresponding special section of the December Issue of JEDM in 2022.

For the ninth time, EDM 2023 will hold a Journal track allowing papers submitted to JEDM to be presented at the conference. The JEDM Track at EDM 2023 received five submissions, among which two made it to the final stage in time for publication in this issue. We are pleased to publish the following works.

In the first paper, **Ryan S. Baker, Lief Esbenshade, Jonathan Vitale, and Shamyia Karumbaiah** revisit the problem of feature selection to predict students' outcomes. They focus on whether demographic variables should be included in the process from a fairness point of view. After reviewing arguments in favor of including demographic variables as predictors and against including them, they argue for using demographic variables to validate fairness instead of using them in the prediction task.

In the second paper, **Adam C. Sales, Ethan B. Prihar, Johann A. Gagnon-Bartsch, and Neil T. Heffernan** describe a recent method to improve the precision of randomized A/B testing. Randomized A/B tests can be deployed easily to test different conditions in online platforms. The recent method rests on utilizing the “remnant from an experiment—students who were not randomized between conditions, but for whom covariate and outcome data are available”. The authors present their results of applying the method to 68 A/B education tests run on the ASSISTments platform.

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